

Effect of Biopesticide Neem oil on Amino Acid contents of Foragers honeybee *Apis mellifera* L.

Sushil Kumar

Department of Zoology,
Government PG College, Bisalpur Pilibhit (UP) India

ABSTRACT

The effect sublethal concentrations ($\frac{1}{4}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ of LC_{50} at 96 hrs.) of biopesticide neem oil – 25 EC was studied on the forager bees (25 days old worker bees) of Italian honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. The results indicated that there were no significant alteration in total amino acid contents in forager bees at either sublethal concentration level-1 ($\frac{1}{4}$ of LC_{50} at 96 hrs) or concentration-2 ($\frac{1}{2}$ of LC_{50} at 96 hrs.) of neem oil treated bees over control bees. Although field experiments are inevitable for further confirmations of lethality of neem oil on honeybees. But on the basis of present study, neem oil was found to be safe for bees visiting to blooming crops for nectar collection.

Key words : Neem oil, Forager bees, *Apis mellifera* L. Amino Acids.

INTRODUCTION

It is well understood that honeybees are one of the most important insect to human beings and ecosystem. They help to the farmers by pollinating their crops, fruit trees and to the environment by pollinating wild plants (Adlakha and Dhaliwal, 1979a; Free, 1993). These creatures are also well known for their art of manufacturing the honey, royal jelly, bee wax and propolis. Since historical period, honey is one of the most important natural products of honeybees and has been used as medicine and as an option of hygienic food substitute, especially for new born. (Chakki, 2015).

Globally, Crop protection relies on the use of synthetic pesticides. In the past, synthetic pesticides have played a major role in crop protection programs and have immensely benefited mankind. The discovery and use of DDT in 1940 and then BHC and subsequent development of the chlorinated cyclodienes marked a major advance in the field of crop protection. These chemicals have made great contributions to plant protection but have also raised a number of ecological and medical problems (Varma and Dubey, 1999).

Nevertheless, their indiscriminate use has resulted in the development of resistance by pests (insects, weeds, etc), resurgence and outbreak of new pests, toxicity to non-target organisms and hazardous effects on the environment endangering the sustainability of ecosystems (Jeyasankar and Jesudasan, 2005).

Non-target insects such as honeybees, which are economically and socially important to human beings, are also effected or killed in the process of pest control (Johansen 1979, Atkins, *et al.*, 1975). Pesticides cause not only morphological but physiological dysfunction also to the bees when their applications are repeated. In such cases it is not the bee mortality, which is significant, but it may reduce longevity (Mackenzie and Wiston, 1989) and biochemical imbalance. The toxic effect of pesticides on the level of ions and amino acids was reported by Reddy (1983) in *Apis cerena indica*. Organophosphates have been reported to be neuroactive poison and toxic for amino acid metabolism in *Apis mellifera* (Kumar 2017). They act at the synapses of the neurons (Srivastava, 1993) and have been found very toxic to honeybees (Kumar and Gupta, 2007). Gupta and Kumar (2003) reported the quantitative analysis of the essential and nonessential amino acids present in adult honeybee workers as their dry body weight. The description provided above no doubt, shows that synthetic pesticides have been very toxic to bees.

The ideal insecticide should control target pests adequately and should be target-specific (*ie.* It should be able to kill the pest insect but not other insects or animals), rapidly degradable, and low in toxicity to humans and other mammals (Atawodi and Atawodi, 2009). Two classes of insecticides that exhibit some of these characteristics are the botanical insecticides and the insecticidal soaps. Botanical insecticides, sometimes referred to as “botanicals,” are naturally occurring insecticides have been derived from plants. Insecticidal soaps are soaps that have been selected and formulated for their insecticidal action (Weinzierl and Henn, 1991). So there has always been a need of an ideal pesticide which could work on pests but safe to honeybee. Neem oil is one of that type of botanical insecticides which is effective on pests but safe for human being and bees (Esparza-Díaz 2010). Keeping in mind this aspect, we used a very popular biopesticide Neem oil (25 EC) to understand the effect of it on amino acid contents of honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. This work reports the quantitative changes in the amino acids

contents of foragers of *A. mellifera* L. measured as their dry matter under stress of biopesticide neem oil at two different concentrations of it.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

NEEM OIL

It is a bio-pesticides obtained from a most useful plant *Azadirachta indica*. Now a days its formulation as 25 EC and 500 ppm are being used against the pests of mustard crop, stored grain pests like *Sitophilus*, *Rhizopertha* etc. and soil pests. This biopesticide has a chemical called as Azadirachtin. Its application has proved to be one of the best botanical pesticides having least toxicity for mammals including human beings and plants on which it is sprayed. This pesticide used in present study was manufactured by M/s. Hindustan Crop Science Limited, Delhi. In present study two different concentration levels of pesticides were used, which are level-1 and level-2.

BEE REARING

The target organism Italian honeybee, *Apis mellifera* L. was reared in Environmental Research Laboratory, Zoology Department, Govt PG College Bisalpur Pilibhit using standard Langstroth cages with wax sheet foundation frame under controlled conditions. The bee colonies were acclimatized for five days in the cages before toxicity tests. The temperature and relative humidity maintained were 20-25°C (± 2 °C) and 61-66 R.H., respectively.

In order to carryout toxicological assay, four replicates of control and treated worker bees of 25 days old were used. For biochemical analysis worker bees were collected with a cotton cone net trapper from the landing board as they departed. The control bee colonies were fed on 50% sugar syrup. The treated bee colonies were fed on pesticides mixed ($\frac{1}{4}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ of LC₅₀ at 96 hours) 50% sugar syrup. The bee colonies were exposed up to four days continuously.

ESTIMATION OF AMINO ACIDS

Samples of 30 forager bees were collected randomly from each of the four replicates of control and treated bee colonies. The individuals were randomly selected for analysis from control and treated colonies. After the removal of gut contents, they were dried to constant weight under vacuum at 40 °C and their amino acid contents were determined. Duplicate analysis on foragers bees for nitrogen were performed by a micro-kjeldal method (Yuen and Pollard, 1953) and amino acids were analysed by a single-column buffer system after acid hydrolysis. The nitrogen analysis enabled the amino acid analyses to be expressed as gram per 16 gram of nitrogen.

A Technicon amino acid auto analyzer (114-AAA, Technicon Instruments Limited, U.K.) was used to separate the amino acids with a modified Thomson and Miles (1964) buffer system in single columns (Waring and Bolton, 1967). 9% cross-linking : average particle size 24 μ m was used as cationic resin. The colour reagent was 2, 4, 6 - trinitrobenzene sulphonic acid. The pumping rate was adjusted to 0.9 ml/min. Each chromatogram took about 10 hours to complete. Norleucine was used as an internal standard. In no case the standard error of the mean colour factor for any amino acid was greater than ± 0.02 . The test of significance was calculated by adopting Fisher's 't' test at $p < 0.05^*$, $p < 0.01^{**}$ and $p < 0.001^{***}$.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The findings of amino acid analysis of Neem oil treated worker honeybees are presented in table-1 and Fig-1. An analysis of variance of these results indicated that there were no significant alteration in total amino acid contents in forager bees at conc. level-1 and conc. level-2 of neem oil in treated bees over control bees. The amino acids that showed significant changes at conc. level-1 over control were cystine (-20.68 %**), methionine (+26.31 %**), phenyl alanine (-15.38%), lysine (+20.00%*). However, conc. level-2 of neem oil, also caused deviation on methionine (-10.31 %*) and lysine (-12.00%*) amino acids of treated foragers over control bees. Overall, neem oil caused a little bit changes (\pm) in total amino acid contents of treated bees over control bees (Table-1 and Fig-1)) which is insignificant regarding amino acid contents.

The relative amount of various amino acids in the control and neem oil treated forager honeybees either at conc. level-1 or conc. Level-2 were not significantly different from the control bees as measured for dry weight of bees. The data presented in table 1 vividly indicate that the treatment of neem oil to the forager bees with respect to both of the concentrations was quite safe to the bees (Srivastava, 1993). Most of the protein in flying insects is due to presence of the flight muscles, of which $\frac{1}{3}$ rd part is mitochondrial protein (Bartelink and De Kort, 1973). Thus, an analysis of the amino acids produced from adult insects

by acid hydrolysis is supposed to be fairly uniform (amino acids level in control bees). Variations in the amino acid composition of insects have been attributed either to the effect of flight metabolism (Bursell, 1963) or to dietary absorption into the haemolymph (Auclair, 1959) or under the effect of pesticides causing decrease or increase acid hydrolysis of proteins (proteolysis) (Reddy, 1983) and in worker honeybees the relative activity of glands producing larval food may also be implicated and it makes a possibility that in honeybees all three factors are involved in the variations observed (Tables-1 and Fig-1).

CONCLUSION

The quantitative changes in the contents of different amino acids under stress of pesticide suggested that pesticides affected the normal selective regulation of amino acids in honeybees. This study justifies that neem oil, used in present investigation had almost null effect on amino acids contents of honeybees except for a few, which showed deviations (Atawodi and Atawodi, 2009). The increase in level of a few amino acids indicates either greater proteolysis or greater catabolization of proteins, and their decrease may show further degradation (Cole, W. H. 1950). The biopesticidal effects of neem oil caused a little inhibition or over activity of the enzymes specifically and selectively resulting insignificant changes in amino acid contents of foragers. Although free flying bee and laboratory reared control bee also exhibited a little variation in amino acid contents (Gupta and Kumar, 2003) but it was quite insignificant. These results are in favour of neem oil to be used as biopesticide to spray on the booming crops to protect them from pest infestation. However, more research is recommended.

Table 1: Analysis of amino acids in forager of honey bee *Apis mellifera* L under stress of biopesticide Neem oil.

Sl. No.	Amino Acids	Control	Neem Oil (25EC) Treated	
			Conc. Level-1	Conc. Level-2
1	Aspartic acid	7.5 ± 1.53	6.9 ± 0.25	7.3 ± 0.59
		(---)	(-8.00)	(-2.66)
2	Threonine	3.9 ± 0.28	4.1 ± 0.21	3.5 ± 0.03
		(---)	(+5.12)	(-2.56)
3	Serine	4.9 ± 0.51	4.3 ± 0.65	4.5 ± 0.81
		(---)	(-12.24)	(-8.16)
4	Glutamic acid	9.8 ± 1.19	10.1 ± 0.42	10.0 ± 0.38
		(---)	(+3.06)	(+2.04)
5	Glycine	7.7 ± 1.01	8.0 ± 0.61	7.4 ± 0.18
		(---)	(+3.89)	(-3.89)
6	Alanine	7.9 ± 1.93	7.3 ± 0.81	7.6 ± 0.11
		(---)	(-7.59)	(-3.79)
7	Valine	5.5 ± 0.98	5.4 ± 0.93	5.8 ± 0.65
		(---)	(-1.82)	(+5.54)
8	Cystine	2.9 ± 0.23	2.3 ± 0.55*	3.0 ± 0.87
		(---)	(-20.68)	(+3.45)
9	Methionine	1.9 ± 0.07	2.4 ± 0.29**	1.7 ± 0.43*
		(---)	(+26.31)	(-10.53)
10	Isoleucine	5.0 ± 0.67	5.2 ± 0.57	4.8 ± 0.07
		(---)	(+4.00)	(-4.00)
11	Leucine	7.8 ± 1.44	7.5 ± 0.37	7.9 ± 0.25
		(---)	(-3.84)	(+1.28)
12	Tyrosine	4.0 ± 0.09	4.1 ± 0.23	3.8 ± 0.15
		(---)	(+2.50)	(-5.00)
13	Phenyl alanine	3.8 ± 0.68	3.3 ± 0.47*	3.7 ± 0.05
		(---)	(-15.38)	(-9.75)
14	Lysine	5.0 ± 0.81	6.0 ± 0.31*	4.4 ± 0.63*
		(---)	(+20.00)	(-12.00)
15	Histidine	2.7 ± 0.13	2.9 ± 0.64	2.6 ± 0.33
		(---)	(+7.41)	(-3.70)
16	Arginine	4.4 ± 0.72	4.3 ± 0.10	4.6 ± 0.26
		(---)	(-2.27)	(+4.54)
Total		84.7 ± 12.99	84.1 ± 9.21	82.6 ± 8.89
		(---)	(-0.71)	(-2.48)

Each value is the mean of four replicates \pm S. E.

Values are significant at * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$.

Values in parentheses are percent decrease or increase over control

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author is grateful to the administration and staff of Government PG College Bisalpur who supported at every step of this work. A special thanks goes to Dr. Himshikha Yadav (Asstt. Prof. Botany, VRAL, Govt Mahila Degree college Bareilly) for her help in technical and statistical analysis of data. My deep gratitude to Mr. Rajesh Gangwar for providing apiary facilities to complete this task.

REFERENCES

1. Adlakha, R. L. and Dhaliwal, H. S. (1979a). Insect pollination of seed cauliflower, *Brassica oleracea* with particular reference to the role of honeybees. *Indian Bee J.* 41 (1-2): 13-16.
2. Atawodi, S.E., & Atawodi, J.C. (2009). *Azadirachta indica* (neem): A plant of multiple biological and pharmacological activities. *Phytochemistry Reviews*, 8, 601–605.
3. Atkins, E. L.; MacDonald, R. L. and Greywood; Hale, E. A. (1975). Repellent additives to reduce pesticide hazards to honeybees; Field tests. *J. Environ. Ent.* 4: 207-210.
4. Auclair, J. L. (1959). The influence of dietary amino acids on the blood amino acids of the German cockroach. *J. Insect Physiol.* 3 : 127-131.
5. Bartelink, A. K. M. and De Kort, P.A.D. (1973). Synthesis of mitochondrial protein in the flight muscles of the Colorado beetle. *Biochem. J.* 136 : 795-802.
6. Bursell, E. (1963). Aspects of the metabolism of amino acids in the testsefly. *J. of Insect Physiol.* 9 : 439-452.
7. Chakki, Rajashekhar (2015). "Agriculture Productivity and Efficiency of Seeds", *Cosmos An International Journal of Management*, 4(2), 12-14.
8. Cole, W. H. (1950). Co-operative determination of amino acid contents and the nutritive value of six selected protein food sources. *Rutger univ., New Brunswick*.
9. Duchateau, G., Florkin, M. and Sarlet, H. (1952). Sur les acides amines libres ou combines sous form non protinique du plasma sanguine de differentes insects. *Arch. Int. Physiol. Biochem.* 60: 539-540.
10. Esparza-Diaz, G., Lopez-Collado, J., Villanueva-Jimenez, J.A., Osorio-Acosta, F. Otero Colina, G., and Camacho-Diaz, E. (2010). Azadirachtin concentration, insecticide efficacy and phytotoxicity of four neem *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. extracts. *Agrociencia*, 44, 821–833.

11. Free, J. B. (1993). Insect pollination of crops. 2nd edition, Academic press, London, U. K.
12. Gupta, A. K. and Kumar, S. (2003). Evaluation of Amino Acid Contents of Adult Worker Bee and Brood of Italian Honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. *Nat. Con.* 15 (2) 214-223.
13. Jeyasankar, A., and Jesudasan, R. W. A. (2005). Insecticidal properties of novel botanicals against a few lepidopteran pests. *Pestology* 29, 42–44.
14. Johanson, C.A. (1979). Honeybee poisoning by chemicals: signs contributing factors, current problems and preventions. *Bee world* 63 (3): 109-127.
15. Kumar S. and Gupta A. K. (2007). Age dependent study of the impacts of certain field pesticides on Acetyl cholinesterase activity in worker bees of Italian honeybee *Apis mellifera* L. *J. Ento Res.* 31(2) 115-119.
16. Kumar S. (2017). Quinalphos induced changes in amino acid contents of forager worker bees *Apis mellifera* L. *Res. J.Pharm. Bio. And Chem. Sci.* 8(3) 512-517.
17. Mackenzie, K.E. and Winston, M.L.(1989). Effects of sub lethal exposure to Diazinon on longevity and temporal division of labor in the honeybees. *J. Econ. Ento.* 82 (1): 75-82.
18. Reddy, C.C. (1983). Effects of pesticides on the level of ions and amino acids in the Haemolymph of worker honeybees. *Indian bee J.* 45(4): 105-107.
19. Srivastava, K. P. (1993). Mode of action of insecticides. *A Text Book of Applied Entomology*, pages 77-98.
20. Thomson, A. R. and Miles, B. J. (1964). Ion exchange chromatography of amino acids: improvement in single column system. *Nature, Lond.* 203 : 483-484.
21. Varma, J., and Dubey, N. (1999). Prospectives of botanical and microbial products as pesticides of tomorrow. *Curr. Sci.* 76, 172–178.
22. Waring, J. J. and Bolton, W. (1967). 2,4,6-trinitrobenzene sulphonic acid as a colour reagent for amino acids analyses. Proc. 5th colloquium in amino acid analysis. *Technichon Mongor.* 2 : 30-34.
23. Weinzierl, R., and Henn, T. (1991). *Alternatives in Insect Management: Biological and Biorational Approaches*. Urbana, IL: North central regional extension publication.
24. Yuen, S. H. and Pollard, A. G. 1953. Determination of nitrogen in soil and plant materials; use of boric acid in micro-kjeldal method. *J. Sci. Fd. Agric.* 4 : 490-496.